

DABCO-catalysed one-pot synthesis of furo[3,2-*c*]coumarin from 3-halochromone

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Abstract : A highly efficient synthesis of furo[3,2-*c*]coumarins have been achieved by a DABCO-catalysed reaction of 3-halochromones with 4-hydroxycoumarin. DABCO was found to be the most efficient catalyst among the different bases used for this reaction.

Keywords : Chromone, 3-halochromone, DABCO, furo[3,2-*c*]coumarin, 1-benzopyran.

Introduction

Furocoumarins are present in large number of biologically active natural products¹. Furo[3,2-*c*]-1-benzopyran framework is present in coumestrol, wedelolactone, medicagol and plicadin (Fig. 1), which possess potent physiological activities². Earlier syntheses

Fig. 1. Different naturally occurring compounds having furo[3,2-*c*]coumarin skeleton.

of substituted furo[3,2-*c*]coumarins include (i) rhodium(II)-catalysed heterocyclization of 3-diazobenzopyran-2,4(3*H*)-dione³, (ii) CAN-mediated [3+2] cyclization of 4-hydroxycoumarin with terminal alkynes⁴, (iii) cascade addition/cyclization/oxidation of 3-alkynylchromones⁵, (iv) reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with α -haloketone⁶ and (v) isocyanide-induced multicomponent reaction involv-

ing 3-formylchromone and 4-hydroxycoumarin⁷. Herein, we report an efficient one-pot DABCO-catalysed synthesis of furo[3,2-*c*]coumarins.

Chromones having a suitable functionality at its C-3 position have been utilised as a useful building block for the synthesis of different heterocycles⁸. 3-Halochromone **1** also acts as a template for the synthesis of different heterocyclic compounds⁹. Compound **1** has been utilised successfully in Suzuki-coupling reaction for the synthesis of isoflavones¹⁰ and also in Heck-coupling reaction¹¹.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

In an endeavour to synthesise chromenylcoumarin, a

mixture of **1** (X = Br), 4-hydroxycoumarin (**2**), Pd(OAc)₂, Ph₃P and triethylamine was heated under reflux in acetonitrile for 6 h. The reaction mixture afforded a yellow solid **3**. Literature survey revealed that 3-bromochromone produces 3-salicyloylfuran derivatives when treated with β -diketones or β -ketoesters in the presence of DBU or DBN but failed to do so in presence of Et₃N¹². To check the role of Pd(OAc)₂ in the present reaction, compound **1** (X = Br) was heated with **2** in the presence of Et₃N in acetonitrile and interestingly the reaction mixture also produced **3** in comparable yield, but in the absence of Et₃N there was no reaction (Table 1, entries 1 and 2).

placed by **1** (X = I), but the latter required a little longer reaction time to complete the reaction (entries 11,12).

To consider the effect of solvent in this reaction an equimolar mixture of **1**, **2** and DABCO was heated under reflux in different solvents like acetonitrile, methanol, DCM, THF and toluene. Among these solvents, acetonitrile was found to be the best solvent.

In conclusion, we have achieved the synthesis of hitherto unreported furocoumarins from the reaction of 3-halochromone and 4-hydroxycoumarin by a one-pot organo-catalysed reaction. DABCO was found to be the most efficient catalyst in this process.

Table 1. Reaction of 3-halochromone **1** with 4-hydroxycoumarin (**2**) under different conditions

Entry	1		Base	Time (h)	Product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
	R	X					
1	H	Br	Et ₃ N ^a	6	3a	60	166-168
2	H	Br	-	9	NR	-	-
3	H	Br	DABCO	5	3a	90	166-168
4	H	Br	Pyridine ^a	9	3a	55	166-168
5	H	Br	DMAP ^a	5	3a	74	166-168
6	H	Br	DBU ^a	5	3a	79	166-168
7	Me	Br	DABCO	5	3b	85	242-244
8	Cl	Br	DABCO	5	3c	80	246-248
9	Br	Br	DABCO	5	3d	90	254-256
10	H	I	DABCO (1.5 eq)	4	3a	81	166-168
11	H	I	DABCO	6	3a	80	166-168
12	Cl	I	DABCO	6	3c	70	246-248

^aNR stands for no reaction; ^a2 equivalents of base were used.

The formation of **3** can be explained as follows : under the reaction conditions Michael addition of the enolate of 4-hydroxycoumarin to 3-halochromone **1** forms **4** and then generates an α -haloketone **5**, a perfect electrophile for intramolecular S_N2 by the oxygen end of the enolate. Subsequent transformation to furocoumarin **3** is facile via **6** due to the thermodynamic stability of the product **3**.

The effect of different bases as catalyst in this reaction was also tested. DABCO was found to be the most efficient catalyst among Et₃N, pyridine, DMAP, DBU and DABCO. One equivalent of DABCO can complete the reaction, whereas other bases required two equivalents (entries 1-9). Use of 1.5 equivalents of DABCO with respect to **1** and **2** shortens the reaction time without improving the yield of the product (entry 10). The reaction produced similar results when **1** (X = Br) was re-

Experimental

All reagents were purchased from commercial sources and used as such unless stated otherwise. The products were purified by column chromatography over silica gel (100-200). The recorded m.p.s are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Beckman IR 20a, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra on a Bruker 300 MHz and 75 MHz spectrometer, respectively in CDCl₃; mass spectra were recorded on a Qtof Micro YA 263 instrument and elemental analysis on a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. Light petroleum refers to the fraction with 60-80 °C.

Typical procedure for the synthesis of **3a** :

A solution of **1** (R = H, X = Br) (0.5 mmol, 112 mg), 4-hydroxycoumarin (**2**) (0.5 mmol, 80 mg) and DABCO (0.5 mmol, 60 mg) in acetonitrile (5 mL) was

heated under reflux for 5 h. Solvent from the reaction mixture was removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass was stirred with water, filtered and the solid was washed with water and dried in air. The crude product was purified by flash chromatography using 1 : 1 mixture of petroleum ether and benzene to produce **3a** (138 mg, 90%).

2-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)-4H-furo[3,2-c]chromen-4-one (3a) :

Yellow crystalline solid; m.p. 166–168 °C; IR (KBr) : 1489, 1535, 1597, 1630, 1765, 3130 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.01–7.11 (2H, m), 7.42–7.51 (2H, m), 7.56–7.68 (2H, m), 7.81 (1H, s), 8.05 (1H, br d, J 7.8 Hz), 8.15 (1H, br d, J 7.8 Hz), 11.70 (1H, s, exchangeable); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 111.5, 111.7, 117.6, 118.1, 118.3, 118.8, 119.4, 121.9, 125.1, 130.7, 132.8, 137.0, 151.9, 153.7, 157.1, 159.7, 163.3, 184.4; MS : m/z 307 ($M + H^+$), 329 ($M + Na^+$) (Found : C, 70.36; H, 3.19. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$: C, 70.59; H, 3.29%).

2-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzoyl)-4H-furo[3,2-c]chromen-4-one (3b) :

Yellow crystalline solid; m.p. 242–244 °C; IR (KBr) : 1450, 1545, 1635, 1760, 3200 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.39 (3H, s), 7.01 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.39–7.52 (3H, m), 7.64–7.69 (1H, m), 7.79 (1H, s), 7.89 (1H, s), 8.05 (1H, br d, J 7.5 Hz), 11.49 (1H, s, exchangeable) (Found : C, 71.09; H, 3.69. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$: C, 71.25; H, 3.78%).

2-(5-Chloro-2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4H-furo[3,2-c]chromen-4-one (3c) :

Yellow crystalline solid; m.p. 246–248 °C; IR (KBr) : 1440, 1550, 1590, 1640, 1750, 3250 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.08 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 7.45–7.56 (3H, m), 7.65–7.71 (1H, m), 7.89 (1H, s), 8.05 (1H, dd, J 7.8, 1.2 Hz), 8.21 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 11.69 (1H, s, exchangeable) (Found : C, 63.58; H, 2.60. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_9\text{ClO}_5$: C, 63.45; H, 2.66%).

2-(5-Bromo-2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4H-furo[3,2-c]chromen-4-one (3d) :

Yellow crystalline solid; m.p. 254–256 °C; IR (KBr) : 1450, 1545, 1650, 1740, 3257 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.02 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 7.45–7.54 (2H, m), 7.65–7.71 (2H, m), 7.89 (1H, s), 8.06 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 1.2 Hz), 8.36 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 11.71 (1H, s, exchangeable) (Found : C,

56.01; H, 2.29. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_9\text{BrO}_5$: C, 56.13; H, 2.36%).

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